

Cleaning Up Crude And Engine Oil Pollution With The Fungus *Ganoderma Sessile*: A Hands-On Research Project To Train Environmental Technology Students

Lauretta N. Ofofile, Goodness D. Obayemi, Omalabake O. Asulewon

¹Environmental Biology Unit, Department of Biological Science,
Yaba College of Technology. P.M.B 2011, Yaba Lagos Nigeria

Corresponding Author: Lauretta N. Ofofile

Abstract

Some *Ganoderma* mushrooms are reported to biodegrade hydrocarbons using their enzymatic system. This paper reports on the capability of *Ganoderma sessile* to degrade crude oil and spent engine oil (SEO) in liquid cultures using mycoremediation techniques. It also acts as an outline for embedding practical bioremediation research into the TVET curriculum, which aims to build hands-on skills in fungal culturing, pollution control and hydrocarbon degradation analysis. Considering the critical environmental destruction caused by petroleum pollutants, the research assesses mycoremediation as environmental cleanup method. An active culture of *G. sessile* that was prepared in potato dextrose agar was subcultured using the same medium. The seven-day old mycelial culture of the *G. sessile* was inoculated in a mineral salt in 1L of water contaminated with 20% and 30% each of crude oil or SEO and incubated for 30 days. UV-Vis spectroscopy was used to monitor the mycelia growth, measuring absorbance at 600 nm, while the hydrocarbon degradation was assessed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). *G. sessile* showed moderate growth with a distinct decline phase. In SEO-contaminated media, *G. sessile* showed robust growth. GC-MS analysis confirmed that *Ganoderma sessile* significantly degraded hydrocarbons, particularly BTEX compounds (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene) and some polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), though some high-molecular-weight hydrocarbons persisted. The study highlights the *Ganoderma* species as an effective bioremediation agent, showing promise in SEO degradation. These findings underscore fungal mycoremediation as a viable, eco-friendly approach to petroleum pollution cleanup. This procedure should be incorporated into the environmental technology laboratory curriculum for training students to design community-led oil spill response projects using local fungal species.

Keywords: *Ganoderma*, Biodegradation, Skills, Mycelia and Spectroscopy

INTRODUCTION

The Niger Delta region in Nigeria stands as the largest wetland in Africa and one of the largest in the world [1]. The local oil industry has played a significant role in the country's growth and development. Unfortunately, unsustainable oil exploration activities in the region have resulted in it being among the five most severely petroleum-contaminated ecosystems globally. In 2020 and 2021, Nigeria's National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA) recorded 822 combined oil spills, totaling 28,003 barrels of oil spewed into the environment [2]. Crude oil is a naturally occurring liquid mixture made up of hydrocarbons [3]. The increasing frequency of petroleum pollution by crude oil in developing nations like Nigeria has led to severe environmental degradation, particularly in ecologically sensitive regions such as the Niger Delta. Conventional remediation techniques, including physical and chemical cleanup methods, are often expensive, environmentally invasive, and inaccessible to resource-limited communities [4]. As a result, there is a growing need for cost-effective, sustainable, and community-adaptable solutions like

mycoremediation, which utilizes fungal organisms to degrade hydrocarbons naturally.

In research by Loyd et al. (5), *G. sessile*, caused the decay of all tested wood types, demonstrating their ability to attack all cell wall components causing the most decay across all wood types on average, highlighting its robust enzymatic system. Castellanos De La Cruz et al. [6] reported that nine fungal species showed different levels of tolerance to Cu²⁺ concentrations ranging from 30 to 100 mg/L. Among them, the *Ganoderma lucidum* H14-35 strain exhibited the highest biosorption capacity, achieving up to 76.97% at Cu²⁺ concentrations of 30 and 60 mg/L. Despite the promise shown by fungi, particularly *Ganoderma* species, in hydrocarbon degradation, their potential remains largely underexplored in local bioremediation programs and even less integrated into vocational training systems. This disconnect creates a lack of skills among students in the fields of science laboratory technology (environmental biology) who cannot obtain hands-on experience with environmental biotechnics in laboratories [7].

In addition to evaluating the mycoremediation ability of *G. sessile*, this project aimed to give science laboratory technology students hands-on laboratory experience. It offered the students the opportunity to learn how to grow fungi, test hydrocarbon degradation and the use of spectroscopy. The study also shows how TVET programs can use scientific research to teach students pollution control and bioremediation methods. Filamentous fungi such as *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus* species, have been investigated for the degradation of aliphatic hydrocarbons, chlorophenols and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, with the organic pollutants serving as carbon and energy sources [8]; [9]. The potentials of bacteria to remediate soil that has been contaminated with petroleum hydrocarbons and dangerous metals have been studied. However, there is a paucity of information on the ability of fungi to degrade both kinds of contaminants in the environment [9].

Furthermore, Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) sector in Nigeria pays attention to conventional skill areas like mechanics, welding and construction without much emphasis on bio-based environmental technologies. Although these technologies are essential for confronting new issues such as oil spill cleanup and ecosystem repair [10]. This study, therefore, reports the investigation into the ability of *Ganoderma sessile*, to degrade petroleum products (crude oil and spent engine oil) in liquid medium. Also to equip environmental science students with practical skills in culturing fungi, preparing contaminated media, conducting spectrophotometric and GC-MS analyses, and interpreting bioremediation data.

OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate the mycoremediation ability of *G. sessile* using crude and engine oil
2. To give science laboratory technology students hands-on laboratory experience on growing fungi, test hydrocarbon degradation and the use of spectroscopy

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

The active mycelia cultures of the mushroom; *G. sessile* grown in agar (Potato Dextrose Agar) plates were collected from the Mushroom Research and Training Laboratory, Yaba College of Technology. Petroleum products (crude oil and spent engine oil) were collected from Mechanic workshops and Oil Company in Lagos. The mycelia cells of *G. sessile* were subcultured on potato dextrose agar (PDA). The seven-day fungal cultures were grown in special enhancement growth media, mineral salt stock solution (MSSS) and modified minimum salt solution (MSS) and used for the experiment.

Preparation of Mineral Salt Solution (MSS) and Contamination with Petroleum Products

The method used was modified by Adedokun & Ataga (11). Mineral salts liquid medium (MSM) comprised of the basal medium and trace elements in ratio 9:1. Streptomycin (0.1g) was added to the homogenized medium to prevent any form of bacterial contamination. Mineral salt in 1L of distilled water comprised of: KH_2PO_4 (1g), $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.4g), $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5g), $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.5g), $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.08g), $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (6 mg), $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5 mg), $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4 mg), $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 mg), Thiamine HCL (1 mg), Pyridoxine HCL (1 mg), Nicotinic acid (1 mg), Yeast Extract (25g), NaCl (0.1g), Glucose (30g). The contamination of the mineral salt solution with crude oil and S.E.O was done according to the method described by Adedokun & Ataga (11). The effect of the growth of mycelia of *G. sessile* on crude oil and SEO in liquid medium were quantified by testing for the Optical Density on an interval of 7 days and finally carrying out a GC/MS test at the end to serve as a confirmatory test.

Spectrophotometric Analysis

To ascertain the optimal wavelength for absorbance (turbidity) of the cultured sample obtained via the extraction protocol, samples underwent scanning across the wavelength spectrum of 200–800 nm using the Ultra-Violet -Visible Spectroscopy (AtIco Double beam UV-visible spectrophotometer). This was done using the modified method used by Alsberi et al. (12). Absorbance readings were obtained and utilized to calculate optical density using the following formula:

$$O.D = -\log_{10}(1/Abs)$$

Where O.D represents Optical Density and *Abs* signifies Absorbance.

The resulting data was plotted to illustrate the variation in the peak of optical densities among the Control, 20% oil-contaminated, and 30% oil-contaminated cultures in the presence of *G. sessile* mycelia. Optical density measurements were recorded after 30 days (1 month) of incubation.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy Analysis

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy Analysis was performed using the method used by Ranjan et al. (13). Samples (digested) were analyzed by gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC/MS), using Agilent-Technologies (Little Falls, CA, USA) 6890N Network GC system, equipped with an AgilentTechnologies 5975 inert XL Mass selective detector and Agilent- Technologies 7683B series auto injector. This is according to the method used by Fey (14), samples were further identified and authenticated using their MS spectra compared to

those from the NIST mass spectral library of the GC/MS system

Technical Skills Acquired: Skills acquired that are transferable include the following

1. Mycelial isolation and subculturing
2. Preparation of mineral salt media
3. Controlled contamination with hydrocarbons
4. Spectrophotometric analysis (UV-Vis)
5. GC-MS sample handling and interpretation

RESULTS

Fungal Growth rate of *Ganoderma sessile* on minimal salt solution contaminated with crude oil and spent engine oil

The results of growth kinetics of the mycelia culture of *G. sessile* in the liquid medium contaminated with crude oil and spent engine oil over a 28-day incubation period investigated using Ultra-Violet Visible Spectroscopy to quantify media Absorbance at 600nm wavelength are shown in the images in Figure 1. This result provides training opportunities in data recording, fungal growth monitoring, and result interpretation of key competencies for environmental lab technicians.

The mycelia growth of *G. sessile* on minimal salt solution contaminated with crude oil

Figure 1, image 1 illustrates the growth dynamics of the mycelia of *G. sessile* over a 28-day incubation period in cultures contaminated with 20% and 30% crude oil. The result of absorbance at 600nm utilizing UV-Spectrophotometry revealed, through the measure of turbidity, a pronounced exponential growth of *G. sessile* cells within enriched liquid media supplemented with crude oil at concentrations of 20% and 30%.

The mycelia growth of *G. sessile* on minimal salt solution contaminated with spent engine oil

Growth of *G. sessile* in liquid culture contaminated with 20% and 30% S.E.O measured with absorbance at 600nm over a 28-day incubation period are shown in Figure 1, image 2.

The growth dynamics of *Ganoderma* fungi species: *G. sessile* under 20% and 30% S.E.O contamination revealed *G. sessile* exhibited moderate growth, with a lag phase followed by exponential increase and subsequent decline under both S.E.O concentrations. Despite the decline in post-peak, *G. sessile* demonstrated substantial growth.

Optical Density of Crude oil degraded by the *G. sessile*

Figure 1, image 3 shows the optical density of 20% and 30% Crude oil after a 30-day incubation period with *G. sessile* across wavelengths ranging from 200-800nm. The graphs depict the level of degradation of oil contaminants by mycelia. The optical density of the crude oil typically decreased with increased wavelengths.

The optical density of crude oil degraded by *G. sessile* peaked at 300nm above 2. The OD decreased to below 1 for 20% crude oil at 800nm but by 30%, it decreased to slightly above 1.5 at 600 nm and had a slight increase above the control for the oil (Figure 1, image 3).

Optical Density of Spent Engine Oil degraded by the *G. sessile*

The optical density (OD) of 20% and 30% S.E.O incubated with *G. sessile*, peaked at 500 nm above 2. The OD decreased to below 0.5 at 800nm for 20% S.E.O but by 30%, it decreased to slightly lower at the same wavelength (Figure 1, image 4). The control, on the other hand, had an OD of 1.5 at 800 nm.

Figure 1: Fungal growth and Optical Density. Images 1-2 are *G. sessile* growth curve in liquid growth media contaminated with crude oil. *G. sessile* growth curve in liquid growth media contaminated

with S.E.O. Images 3-4 Optical density of 20% and 30% crude oil incubated with the liquid culture of *G. sessile* after 30 days, and Optical density of 20% and

30% S.E.O incubated with the liquid culture of *G. sessile* after 30 days respectively.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy of crude oil and spent engine oil degraded by *G. sessile*

The results illustrated in the images in Figure 2 are the chromatograms from the GC-MS analysis of the controls: crude oil (30%) without the mycelial culture of *Ganoderma* (C.O) and spent engine oil (30%) without the mycelia culture of *Ganoderma* (S.E.O); Crude oil (30%) after 30 days incubation with the mycelial culture of *G. sessile*, and Spent engine oil (30%) after 30 days incubation with the mycelial culture of the *G. sessile*. Hydrocarbons, as well as volatile organic compounds, completely degraded by *G. sessile* in crude oil include 5-ethyl-2-methylheptane, 2,6,10-trimethylpentadecane, propylcyclohexane, 1,2,3,5-tetramethylbenzene, with compounds like heneicosane, tricosane and 1-ethyl-4-methylbenzene, reducing significantly but not

completely as evident by the flattening of peaks in the figure 2A below.

Hydrocarbons, as well as volatile organic compounds, completely degraded by *G. sessile* in S.E.O include 1-ethyl-1-methylcyclopropane, 1-methyl-2-propylbenzene, and 1-methyl-3-propylbenzene, with compounds like dodecane, tridecane and 2-ethyl-1,4-dimethylbenzene reducing significantly but not completely as evident by the flattening of peaks in the figures 2B below.

This result provides training opportunities in skills in interpreting chromatographic and mass spectral data, identifying compounds, and quantifying analytes using calibration techniques. It also builds competence in sample preparation, method development, instrument troubleshooting, and data reporting— key competencies for environmental lab technicians.

Figure 2: Chromatogram from the GC-MS of liquid culture of *Ganoderma sessile* with or without crude oil and spent engine oil. A: Images 1 and 2 are Chromatogram from GC- MS test result of liquid media containing 30% Crude oil after 30 days without organism and Chromatogram from GC- MS test result of liquid media inoculated with *G. sessile* containing 30% Crude oil after 30 days respectively. **B:** Images 1 and 2 are Chromatogram from GC- MS test result of liquid media containing 30% S.E.O after

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Mycelial Growth culture of *Ganoderma sessile* in crude oil and spent engine oil contaminated medium

To accomplish the objectives of this study, which was to explore the capabilities of *G. sessile*, to degrade crude oil and spent engine oil, a series of experiments were conducted utilizing their mycelial cultures. The fungal mycelia were cultivated in an enriched media containing 20% and 30% concentrations each of crude oil and S.E.O. To assess the mycelial growth of the *Ganoderma* species,

the absorbance at 600nm in ultraviolet- visible spectroscopy was measured at 7-day intervals over a 28-day incubation period. The turbidity of the liquid cultures was read at 7-day intervals to determine growth progress. Increase in turbidity over the incubation time was suggested as the increase in cell growth which implies a growth in hypha [15]. According to Roshandel (16), the growth of the fungus *Pleurotus florida* was inhibited with increasing concentration of gas oil, a sign of toxicity at high concentrations of the pollutant which could be the reason for poor mycelial growth of *G. sessile* in

30% crude oil-contaminated medium. Furthermore, the greatest growth was slightly higher in the presence of 30% S.E.O. than 20% S.E.O. This divergence can be attributed to contaminants, oil components, and the effect of concentration gradients on the mycelia culture [17]. These results confirm that *G. sessile* can effectively consume hydrocarbons, allowing used engine oil and crude oil to be broken down [18]. High levels of tolerance and acceptability to S.E.O. contamination were also demonstrated by *G. sessile*.

The Optical Density of Spent Engine Oil and Crude Oil Degraded by the mycelia of *Ganoderma sessile*

As the hydrocarbons were broken down into smaller components, their concentration reduced, which was reflected in the reduction in optical density [19]. It's interesting to note that *G. sessile* mycelial growth increased with decreasing crude oil content. This highlights the complexity of fungal reactions to environmental substrates and poisons by illustrating the species-specific response of *Ganoderma* spp. to crude oil concentrations [20]. Lower optical densities at lower concentrations suggest a better growing environment for the fungus [21].

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS) profile of crude oil and spent engine oil degraded by *Ganoderma sessile*

The original hydrocarbon quantity in crude and spent engine oil were determined using GC-MS and compared them with the composition after 30-day incubation. These results showed concentration of some hydrocarbons or their total breakdown into shorter chain hydrocarbons as displayed on the GC-MS profiles [9].

The data in figure 2 confirmed the above results, which catalogue hydrocarbons classified under two broad categories: Aromatic components (monoaromatics, diaromatics, and polyaromatics) and aliphatic components (cyclic and noncyclic hydrocarbons).

Ganoderma sessile showed tremendous ability in the breakdown of many hydrocarbons constituting crude oil. Breakdown is extremely unpredictable based on varying classes of hydrocarbons by structural composition, hydrocarbon complexity, and the presence of enzymatic pathways for attack by the fungus [22]. Compounds like octane, undecane, and 3-ethyl-2,5-dimethylhexane were degrading to intermediate levels. Structurally less complicated linear shape makes it easily accessible for enzymes generated by fungi [23]. The complete degradation of acyclic hydrocarbons could be because of their shorter chain lengths and simpler structures that are more susceptible to enzymatic degradation [24].

Enzymatic reaction that breaks ring structures may be inferred as the reason for the total breakdown of two of the cyclic hydrocarbons by *G. sessile*.

Mohammadi-Sichani et al. (25), reported that the partial degradation of other cyclic hydrocarbons suggests structural difficulty that can prevent total enzymatic degradation. The strength of PAH indicates that their strongly bonded ring framework was resistant to fungal damage. However, studies have demonstrated that certain *Ganoderma* species can dissolve PAHs into polar, more soluble metabolites, thereby partially degrading them [26]. The lower molecular weights and greater volatility of these compounds allowed *G. sessile* to completely degrade them to simpler aromatic molecules, as shown by the total conversion of three BTEX compounds to lower hydrocarbons [22]. The biodegradative potential of these *Ganoderma* fungi is primarily due to their capacity to produce ligninolytic enzymes, which include laccases, manganese peroxidases, and lignin peroxidases. These enzymes aid in the breakdown of complex hydrocarbon structures into simpler molecules [26]. Both cyclic and acyclic hydrocarbons could be biodegraded by *G. sessile* due to their wide variety of enzymes [5]; [27]. GC-MS chromatograms therefore identified the individual compounds degraded by *G. sessile* and evaluated the degree of degradation of the hydrocarbon

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

1. Demonstrates the Bioremediation Potential of *Ganoderma sessile*

The study shows that *Ganoderma sessile* is an effective fungus for breaking down petroleum hydrocarbons, especially BTEX compounds and certain PAHs. This method offers a natural and eco-friendly way to clean up oil-polluted areas.

2. Promotes Practical Environmental Education

The project includes hands-on bioremediation training in the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) curriculum. It gives students skills in fungal culturing, pollution analysis, and techniques for degrading hydrocarbons.

3. Offers a Low-Cost Alternative to Conventional Remediation

This study presents mycoremediation as a sustainable and community-friendly alternative to costly and environmentally harmful chemical or physical cleanup methods. This is especially important for resource-limited areas like the Niger Delta.

4. Strengthens Local Capacity for Environmental Response

By involving students in experimental work, the study builds local skills to design and carry out community-led oil spill response strategies using local fungal species. This helps improve environmental resilience.

CONTRIBUTES TO SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE AND INNOVATION IN TVET

The research addresses a knowledge gap regarding fungi in breaking down petroleum products. It also shows how science-based research can be applied in vocational institutions to encourage innovation and solve real-world problems.

CONCLUSION

G. sessile efficiently degraded BTEX as well as acyclic and cyclic hydrocarbons found in used engine oil and crude oil. The resistance of the PAH chemical suggests a possible obstacle that requires more research to identify more potent therapeutic approaches. The results of the GC-MS study clearly show that *G. sessile* is capable of metabolically converting hydrocarbons into the unique components of crude oil and S.E.O. Additionally, this study promotes a practical, hands-on module for vocational educational institutions that teaches the fundamentals of environmental remediation and supports the role of *Ganoderma sessile* in bioremediation. Results, therefore, emphasize the importance of substrate composition for mycelial development system in fungi and the affinity of the *Ganoderma sessile* mycelial culture to crude oil. Students will be furnished with critical skills for addressing environmental sustainability challenges by gaining hands-on experience in pollution monitoring, spectroscopy, and GC-MS analysis. These bio-based environmental technologies should be embedded into vocational training programs to empower students to lead community-driven oil spill response and ecological restoration efforts.

It is recommended that students should replicate and adapt the bioremediation process using *Ganoderma sessile* to design low-cost, eco-friendly oil spill response systems suitable for local environments.

The study took place in controlled laboratory liquid media and may not fully reflect the complex and changing conditions seen in polluted soils or water, where other biological and chemical factors affect cleanup efforts. Biodegradation was observed over a 30-day incubation period. While this is useful for an initial assessment, longer studies are necessary to understand sustained degradation potential and the stability of by-products over time. The focus was on crude oil and spent engine oil. It did not examine the fungus's ability to break down other petroleum products or mixed pollutants like heavy metals, which are often found together in contaminated areas. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis showed that although *G. sessile* degraded many compounds, some high-molecular-weight polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) were only partially degraded or remained unchanged, suggesting limited enzymatic action on more

complex structures. The study did not compare *G. sessile* to other fungi, bacteria, or groups of microorganisms, so it is unclear if *G. sessile* is effective than other known remediation agents.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nwankwoala, H. O. & Okujagu, D. C. A review of wetlands and coastal resources of the Niger Delta: potential, challenges and prospects. *Environment & Ecosystem Science (EES)*, 5, 37-46. (2021).
- [2] Saint, E. Timeline: Half a century of oil spills in Nigeria's Ogoniland. *Aljazeera*. Date accessed: 11th November 2024. Timeline: Half a century of oil spills in Nigeria's Ogoniland | Environment | Al Jazeera (2022).
- [3] Aljamali, N.M. & Salih, N. S. Review on chemical separation of crude oil and analysis of its components. *Journal of Petroleum Engineering and Technology*, 11(2), 35-49. (2021).
- [4] Ikhumetsa, A. A., Abioye, O. P., Ijah, U. J. J., & Bankole, M. T. A critical review of oil spills in the Niger Delta aquatic environment: causes, impacts, and bioremediation assessment. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 194(816), 1-16. (2022).
- [5] Loyd A. L., Benjamin W. Held, Eric R. Linder, Jason A. Smith, Robert A. Blanchette Elucidating wood decomposition by four species of *Ganoderma* from the United States. *Fungal Biology*, 122(4), 254-263. (2018).
- [6] Castellanos De La Cruz, A., Rincón-Molina, C. I., Manzano-Gómez, L. A., Ruiz-Valdiviezo, V. M., Gen Jiménez, A., Villalobos-Maldonado, J. J., Rincón-Molina, F. A., Garrido-Ramírez, E., & Rincón-Rosales, R. Assessment of Native Wild Macromycete Strains for Mycoremediation of Copper-Contaminated Soils in Coffee Plantations. *Horticulturae*, 10(12),1376. (2024).
- [7] Mishra, M. & Srivastava, D. Mycoremediation: A step towards sustainability. *International Journal of Plant and Environment*, 6(4), 298-303. (2020).
- [8] Asma, B. & Abdelwaheb, C. Biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons by filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus ustus* and *Purpureocillium lilacinum*) isolated from used engine oil contaminated soil. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 41(5), 416-423. (2021).
- [9] Li, Q., Liu, J. & Gadd, G. M. Fungal bioremediation of soil co-contaminated with petroleum hydrocarbons and toxic metals. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 104, 8999-9008. (2020).
- [10] Akhtar, N. & Mannan, M. A. Mycoremediation: Expunging environmental pollutants. *Biotechnology Reports*, 4(5), e00452 (2020).

- [11] Adedokun, O. M. & Ataga, A. E. Oil Spills Remediation using Native Mushroom –A Viable Option. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 8(1), 57-61. (2014).
- [12] Alsberi, H., Hamad, A. A., & Hassan, M. M. Biodegradation of Petroleum Hydrocarbons Using Indigenous Bacterial and Actinomycetes Cultures. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences*, 23(5), 726–734. (2020).
- [13] Ranjan, S., Chaitali, R. O. Y., & Sinha, S. K. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS): a comprehensive review of synergistic combinations and their applications in the past two decades. *Journal of Analytical Sciences and Applied Biotechnology* 5(2), 72-85. (2023).
- [14] Fey, J. A Qualitative Analysis of Bioactive Compounds (Saponins) in Mauby Tree Bark (*Colubrina arborescens*) Using Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS). (Publication No. 13898931) [Dissertation, California State University]. Long Beach ProQuest Dissertations & Theses (2019).
- [15] Mira, P. Yeh, P. & Hall B. G. Estimating microbial population data from optical density. *PLoS ONE* 17(10): e0276040 (2022).
- [16] Roshandel, F., Saadatmand, S., Iranbakhsh, A., & Ardebili, Z. O. Mycoremediation of oil contaminant by *Pleurotus florida* (*P. kumm*) in liquid culture. *Fungal Biology*, 125(9), 667-678. (2021).
- [17] Mohamadhasani, F. & Rahimi, M. Growth response and mycoremediation of heavy metals by fungus *Pleurotus* sp. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1). (2022).
- [18] Beal, J., Farny, N. G., Haddock-Angelli, T., Selvarajah, V., Baldwin, G., Buckley-Taylor, R., Gershater, M., Kiga, D., Marken, J. P., Sanchania, V., Sison, A. & Workman, C. T. Robust estimation of bacterial cell counts from optical density *Communications Biology*, 3(1). (2020).
- [19] Aljeboury, G. H., Dawood, A. T., Khalaf, R. A., Algefari, R. N., Ramadhan, R. S. & Talib, S. S. Isolation of a Novel Bacterium Isolate Capable of Utilizing Crude Oil and Diesel Oil Spills as a Biological Bioremediation Agent. *Frontiers in Bioscience-Elite*, 16(4), 31. (2024).
- [20] Manan, M. A. & Webb, C. Estimating fungal growth in submerged fermentation in the presence of solid particles based on colour development. *Biotechnology & Biotechnological Equipment*, 32(3), 618–627 (2018).
- [2] Shamugam, S. & Kertesz, M. A. Bacterial interactions with the mycelium of the cultivated edible mushrooms *Agaricus bisporus* and *Pleurotus ostreatus*. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 134(1). (2022).
- [22] El-Aziz, A. R. A., Al-Othman, M. R., Hisham, S. M., & Shehata, S. M. Evaluation of crude oil biodegradation using mixed fungal cultures. *PloS one*, 16(8), Article e0256376. (Retracted published 2023, PLoS One, 18(6): e0286773. (2021).
- [23] Agrawal, N., Verma, P., & Shahi, S. K. Degradation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (phenanthrene and pyrene) by the ligninolytic fungi *Ganoderma lucidum* isolated from the hardwood stump. *Bioresources and Bioprocessing*, 5(1), 1-9. (2018).
- [24] Ho, C. L. Comparative Genomics Analysis of *Ganoderma* Orthologs Involved in Plant-Pathogenesis. *Forests*, 14(3), 653. (2023).
- [25] Mohammadi-Sichani, M. E., Mazaheri Assadi, M., Farazmand, A., Kianirad, M., Ahadi, A. M., & Hadian Ghahderijani, H. Ability of *Agaricus bisporus*, *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Ganoderma lucidum* compost in biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbon-contaminated soil. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 16, 2313-2320. (2019).
- [26] Torres-Farradá, G., Manzano-León, A. M., Rineau, F., Ramos Leal, M., Thijss, S., Jambon, I., Put, J., Czech, J., Guerra Rivera, G., Carleer, R. & Vangronsveld, J. Biodegradation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons by native *Ganoderma* sp. strains: identification of metabolites and proposed degradation pathways. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 103, 7203–7215. (2019).
- [27] Okerentugba, P. O., Orji, F. A., Ibiene, A. A. & Elemo, G. N. Spent mushroom compost for bioremediation of petroleum hydrocarbon polluted soil: a review. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Environmental Science and Toxicology*, 4(1), 2–7. (2015).